

Kinetics and Mechanism of Redox Reactions in Partially Aqueous Media. Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Dichloramine-T

B. THIMME GOWDA* and J. ISHWARA BHAT**

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 16 July 1986, revised 8 December 1986, accepted 17 February 1987

Kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by dichloramine-T (DCT), a source of positive chlorine, has been investigated in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium. The rate followed first order kinetics in [DCT], nearly first order in [NCS⁻] and a slight fractional order in [H⁺]. Effects of the added reaction products, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and chloride, and variations in ionic strength and dielectric constant of the reaction medium on the rate have also been investigated. Mechanisms consistent with the observed kinetics have been proposed and the corresponding rate laws deduced. The rate constants for the rate controlling steps have been calculated as functions of temperature. The activation parameters have been computed using these constants.

THE chemistry of *N*-halogeno-*N*-metalloaromatic sulphonamides has attracted the attention of many investigators due to their diverse behaviour. They are sources of halonium cations and hypohalite species¹⁻³. Dichloramine-T is an important member of this class of oxidants. Although the oxidation potential of it has been exploited as an analytical reagent for determining a variety of substrates in solution⁴ there are no reports on the mechanistic investigations with DCT. As a part of our mechanistic investigations with positive halogens⁵⁻⁸ we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by dichloramine-T (*N,N*-dichloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide) in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium. The thiocyanate reactions are of interest due to their analytical, biological and industrial applications. The oxidants so far used for the oxidation of thiocyanate ion include H₂O₂⁹, aqueous iodine¹⁰, Cr^{VI}, V^{VI}, Bi^V and monohalamines⁵⁻⁷.

Experimental

Dichloramine-T (DCT) was prepared by the chlorination of chloramine-T¹¹ in aqueous solutions. The purity of the oxidant was checked by elemental analysis, and iodometric estimation of the active halogen present in it. It was further characterised by recording its ir and nmr spectra. A stock solution of the compound (~0.05 mol dm⁻³) in methanol was prepared, standardised by the iodometric method and preserved in dark-coloured bottles. Potassium thiocyanate (A.R.) was dried at 423 K and its aqueous solution (~0.5 mol dm⁻³) was standardised by argentometric method. All other chemicals used were of accepted grades of purity. Preliminary investigations showed that

the ionic strength of the medium had no effect on the rate.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol under pseudo-first order conditions, with [NCS⁻] >> [DCT] (10-100 times). The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of a measured quantity of DCT solution, thermally equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a mixture containing requisite amounts of thiocyanate solution, HClO₄, methanol and water, equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted DCT at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within ± 3%.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of DCT-NCS⁻ reaction was determined by allowing reaction mixtures containing NCS⁻ and DCT in different ratios to go to completion at different solvent compositions and [H⁺] (0.001-0.10 mol dm⁻³). The sulphate and cyanate ions in the reaction mixtures were detected by standard tests^{14,15}. Sulphate was estimated by gravimetric method¹⁶. *p*-Toluenesulphonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by paper chromatography (R_f=0.91). The observed stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1).

Results

The kinetics of oxidation was investigated at several [DCT]₀, [NCS⁻]₀ and [HClO₄] in 50% (v/v)

** Govinda Dasa College, Suratkal-574 168.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY DICHLORAMINE-T (DCT) IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL MEDIUM AT 303 K

[DCT] $\times 10^4$ mol dm $^{-3}$	[NCS $^{-}$] $\times 10^3$ mol dm $^{-3}$	[HClO $_4$] $\times 10^3$ mol dm $^{-3}$	pH*	k_{obs} $\times 10^3$ s $^{-1}$	[KCl] $\times 10^3$ mol dm $^{-3}$	k_{obs}^{**} $\times 10^3$ s $^{-1}$
1.0	1.0	1.0	2.11	1.65	0.0	1.71
2.0	1.0	1.0	2.10	1.74	0.5	1.71
5.0	1.0	1.0	2.08	1.71	1.0	1.68
10.0	1.0	1.0	2.04	1.61	5.0	1.64
5.0	0.2	1.0	2.05	0.88	10.0	1.51
5.0	0.5	1.0	2.07	0.70	[PTS]	
5.0	1.0	1.0	2.08	1.71	$\times 10^4$ mol dm $^{-3}$	
5.0	2.0	1.0	2.12	2.86	0.0	1.71
5.0	5.0	1.0	2.05	6.88	1.0	1.69
5.0	1.0	0.1	2.68	1.54	5.0	1.66
5.0	1.0	0.2	2.60	1.58	10.0	1.61
5.0	1.0	0.5	2.90	1.68	20.0	1.54
5.0	1.0	1.0	2.08	1.71	% Methanol	
5.0	1.0	2.0	1.85	1.77	10	8.90
5.0	1.0	4.0	1.66	1.91	20	4.80
5.0	1.0	5.0	1.53	2.16	40	2.55
5.0	1.0	10.0	1.34	2.68	50	1.71
					60	1.18
					80	0.68

* Measured pH values of reaction mixtures. ** 10^4 [DCT]=5.0 mol dm $^{-3}$; 10^3 [NCS $^{-}$]=1.0 mol dm $^{-3}$; 10^3 [H $^{+}$]=1.0 mol dm $^{-3}$.

aqueous methanol medium. The plots of $\log ([DCT]_0/[DCT])$ vs time were linear upto at least 75% completion of the reaction and pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in $[DCT]_0$, establishing first order kinetics in $[DCT]_0$. At constant $[DCT]_0$ and $[HClO_4]$, the rate increased with increase in $[NCS^-]$. The $[NCS^-]$ was varied at three different temperatures. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [NCS^-]$ were linear with fractional slopes (~ 0.9) showing fractional order dependence of rate on $[NCS^-]$. The effect of $[H^+]$ on the rate of oxidation was investigated by adding varying amounts of perchloric acid (0.001–0.1 mol dm $^{-3}$) (Table 1). As can be seen $[H^+]$ has little catalysing effect. Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [HClO_4]$ and $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [H^+]_{tr}$ (computed from the measured pH values of the reaction mixtures) were linear with negligible fractional slopes (~ 0.07).

Addition of the reaction product, *p*-toluenesulphonamide (PTS) and Cl^- had negligible effect on the rate. Decrease of dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition from 10/90 to 80/20% (Table 1) decreased the rate. The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed as described under discussion.

Discussion

The kinetics of first order in $[DCT]$, fractional order in $[NCS^-]$ and almost zero order in $[H^+]$ can be accounted by Michaelis–Menton mechanism (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (2),

$$-\frac{d[DCT]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [DCT][HNCS]}{1 + K_1 [HNCS]}$$

$$\text{or } k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [HNCS]}{1 + K_1 [HNCS]} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_1 k_2 [HNCS]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (3)$$

The $[HNCS]$ was varied at three different temperatures and the plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[HNCS]$ were linear with finite intercepts at all temperatures (Fig. 1) in conformity with rate law (3). The formation equilibrium constant (K_1) and decomposition constant (k_2) of the complex were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plots as functions of temperature (Table 2).

The activation parameters were calculated from the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$ and $\log (k_2/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Table 3). The proposed mechanism is also in conformity with the observed non-influence of ionic strength of the medium and the reaction products PTS and Cl^- .

A little dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ may be due to a small fraction of reaction undergoing through Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Fig. 1. (a) Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[NCS^-]$, and (b) Plot of k_{obs} vs $[NCS^-]$, $10^4 [DCT] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3 [HClO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium.

TABLE 2

	Temperature (K)		
	293	303	313
$K_1 (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$	18.28	18.02	20.00
$k_s (\text{s}^{-1})$	0.006	0.011	0.020

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE BY DCT

$\log A$	5.69	$\Delta H^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	41.8
$E_a (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	44.8	$\Delta S^\ddagger (\text{JK}^{-1})$	-144.4
		$\Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	85.6

The corresponding rate law is

$$\frac{-d[DCT]}{dt} = k_s [DCT][H^+] \text{ or } k_{obs} = k_s [H^+] \quad (4)$$

The combined rate law is given by

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [HNCS]}{1 + K_1 [HNCS]} + k_s [H^+] \quad (5)$$

or

$$k_{obs} \approx K_1 k_2 [HNCS] + k_s [H^+] \quad (6)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[HClO_4]$ or $[H^+]_{eff}$ (Fig. 2) and k_{obs} vs $[HNCS]$ (Fig. 1) were linear in agreement with rate law (6).

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]_{eff}$, and (b) Plot of k_{obs} vs $[HClO_4]$; $10^4 [DCT] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3 [NCS^-] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Temp. = 303 K; 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium.

The detailed mechanism of oxidation is shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

The thiocyanic or isothiocyanic acid reacts with dichloramine-T ($RNCl_2$) giving $CINCS$ or $NCSCl$. The $NCSCl$ further reacts with $RNHCl$ and $RNCl_2$ and undergoes hydrolysis in fast steps^{9,10} to give sulphate and cyanate as final products.

The decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium is also in conformity with Amis¹⁷ and other concepts¹⁸.

References

1. F. E. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 742.
2. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, 78, 65.

3. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 323 and references therein.
4. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Talanta*, 1983, 30, 359 and references therein
5. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and N. M. M. GOWDA, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1979, 34, 52.
6. M. S. AHMED, B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 650.
7. B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 1129, 1149, 1987, 26, 215, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1986, 31, 461 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 665.
8. B. T. GOWDA and R. V. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 1021 ; 1986, 25, 578, 908, 1987, 26.
9. I. R. WILSON and G. M. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 4515 ; 1961, 83, 286.
10. G. T. BRIOT and R. H. SMITH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1973, 26, 1863.
11. U. MURALIKRISHNA and K. U. BAPANAIK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 880, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, 256, 225
12. M. H. SMITH and J. I. HABEEB, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 461.
13. T. J. JACOB and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 847.
14. F. FEIGL, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1958 p. 315.
15. E. A. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2577.
16. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1964.
17. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
18. S. G. ENTELLIS and R. P. TIGER, "Reaction Kinetics in the Liquid Phase", Wiley, New York, 1976.